

Electrometric Studies of Binary and Ternary Complexes of Indium(III) with γ -Picoline and Nicotinic Acid

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Manuscript received 23 April 1985, revised 19 May 1986, accepted 23 August 1986

The ternary complexes of In^{III} with γ -picoline and nicotinic acid have been studied polarographically, in aqueous solution at $\text{pH } 4.5 \pm 0.02$ and ionic strength 0.1 (KCl). The reduction of simple ion and its binary and ternary complexes was found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled involving three electrons. A Schaap and McMasters treatment of the observed polarographic data revealed the formation of $[\text{In}-(\text{nico})(\gamma\text{-pico})]^{2+}$, $[\text{In}-(\text{nico})_2(\gamma\text{-pico})]^+$ and $[\text{In}-(\text{nico})(\gamma\text{-pico})_2]^{2+}$ ternary complexes with formation constants $\log \beta_{11} = 3.90$, $\log \beta_{12} = 5.58$ and $\log \beta_{21} = 4.00$.

BINARY¹ and ternary^{2,3} complexes of In^{III} have been studied polarographically in our laboratory. However there are very few references on the electrometric studies of binary and ternary complexes of In^{III} using picolines⁴ and nicotinic⁵ acid. The present paper deals with the results of polarographic investigations of ternary complexes involving In^{III} , γ -picoline and nicotinic acid.

Experimental

Indium nitrate, γ -picoline, nicotinic acid (sodium salt) and potassium chloride and other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Experimental sets were prepared by keeping overall concentration of potassium chloride (base-electrolyte), and In^{III} fixed at 0.1 M and 1 mM, respectively. The method of Deford and Hume⁶ was applied to study the binary complexes of $\text{In}^{\text{III}}-\gamma$ -picoline and $\text{In}^{\text{III}}-\text{nicotinic acid}$ systems separately. The ternary complexes were studied following the method of Schaap and McMasters⁶. The pH of each set was adjusted to 4.5 ± 0.02 , using dilute NaOH/HCl solutions. Nitrogen gas was bubbled through test solutions before recording polarograms.

An automatic pen recording C.I.C. (India) polarograph was used to record polarograms. The capillary had the $m^{2/3} t^{1/3}$ value equal to $2.136 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/3}$ in 1.0 M potassium chloride open circuit at 45 cm effective height of mercury column. A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements. All the observations were made at room temperature ($26 \pm 0.5^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

In^{III} and its complexes under study give very well defined reversible polarographic reduction waves. The slopes of linear plots of $\log i/(i_a - i)$ vs E_a are of the order of $21 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$ and the plots of

i_a vs $\sqrt{h_{\text{corr}}}$ (height of mercury column) are linear and pass through the origin, indicating a three-electron diffusion-controlled reduction in each case at the d.m.e.

The method of Deford and Hume was applied to study the binary complexes of In^{III} with γ -picoline and nicotinate ion separately. The results indicated the formation of successive complexes in each case.

Studies on ternary complexes of $\text{In}^{\text{III}}-\gamma$ -picoline nicotinate system: For the study of ternary complexes the γ -picoline concentration was fixed at 0.1 M. The γ -picoline concentration was so chosen that predominantly one and two γ -picoline molecules respectively would exist in the $\text{In}^{\text{III}}-\gamma$ -picoline system. The nicotinate concentration was varied from 0.0 to 0.2 M for each fixed concentration of γ -picoline. A more electronegative shift was observed in $E_{1/2}$ values indicating the formation of ternary complexes. The functions F_{11} and constants A, B, C and D were calculated by the method of Schaap and McMasters and Laden's^{7,8} extrapolation method, respectively. A Schaap and McMasters treatment of the data (Table 1) reveals the formation of three ternary complexes, viz. $[\text{In}-\gamma\text{-pico}(\text{nicotinate})]^{2+}$, $[\text{In}-(\gamma\text{-pico})_2(\text{nicotinate})]^{2+}$ and $[\text{In}-(\gamma\text{-pico})(\text{nicotinate})_2]^+$ with formation constants $\log \beta_{11} = 3.90$, $\log \beta_{12} = 4.00$ and $\log \beta_{21} = 5.58$, respectively. The mixing constant K_M for the reaction, $1/2[\text{In}-(\gamma\text{-pico})_2]^{2+} + 1/2[\text{In}-(\text{nicotinate})_2]^{2+} = [\text{In}-(\gamma\text{-pico})(\text{nicotinate})]^{2+}$ is a measure of relative stability of ternary complexes in solution as compared to the parent binary complexes. The values of mixing constant $K_M = \beta_{11} \sqrt{\beta_{02} \times \beta_{20}}$ and stabilisation constant $\log K_s = \log K_M - \log 2$, have been calculated⁸, and are $\log K_M = 0.7525$ and $\log K_s = 0.4515$, respectively. The positive value of mixing constant and stabilisation constant reveal that the ternary complexes are slightly more stable than the binary complexes. A schematic representation of the tendency of a ligand to add to a complex

TABLE I—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND F_{10} FUNCTIONS OF In^{III} —NICOTINATE— γ -PICOLINE MIXED SYSTEM

$\text{In}^{\text{III}}=1 \text{ mM}$, $\mu=0.1$ [KCl] $\text{pH}=4.5 \pm 0.02$, $\text{Temp.}=26 \pm 0.5^\circ$, γ -Picoline= 0.1 M (fixed), $-E_{(1/2)_s}(\text{In})=0.610$, $\alpha_d=64$

Sl. no.	Concn. of nicotinic acid	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SOE	α_d (div)	$F_{00}(xy)$	$F_{10}(xy)$	$F_{20}(xy) \times 10^{-2}$	$F_{30}(xy) \times 10^2$
1.	0.01	0.628	60	8.778	78.0	—	—
2.	0.02	0.632	58	14.51	325.5	—	—
3.	0.03	0.644	55	62.36	1812.0	27.06	—
4.	0.04	0.654	53	208.70	5017.5	100.43	15.10
5.	0.05	0.660	52	429.50	8430.0	148.60	21.72
6.	0.06	0.666	50	902.00	1490.0	291.66	31.93

A=8, B=1 000, C=40 000, D=1 500 000.

and to substitute another ligand is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

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